

Emerging Trends of Commercial Farming: A Case Study on Chakhesang Tribe in Nagaland

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Abstract

The habitat of tribal communities worldwide is renowned for their rich and diverse biodiversity. The land inhabited by the Chakhesang tribe in Nagaland is particularly abundant in fertile land, with luxuriant growth of wild crops, fruits, and vegetables, all of which sustain their subsistence economy. However, recently, there has been a noticeable shift towards small-scale commercial farming among the Chakhesang tribe. This significant shift requires a sociological understanding due to its implications for this indigenous community. This empirical study was conducted in 18 villages and four small towns, covering 280 households in the Phek district of Nagaland. Data was collected through personal interviews, observations, and group discussions. The study found that commercial farming has improved income and social status, especially among women. Additionally, it indirectly promotes the preservation of indigenous knowledge and strengthens community bonds among the Chakhesang community. Despite these positive impacts, commercial farming faces challenges, particularly the need for more infrastructure logistics and organized market facilities for the farmers.

Keywords: Agriculture, Chakhesang Nagas, commercial farming, market, tribe, and women.

Introduction:

When the industrialization of agriculture and the consolidation of capitalism as the dominant global socio-economic system began to push small farms to the corners, several agrarian questions emerged, debating the survival and viability of peasantry. (Akram-Lodhi 2021: 687–714, Bernstein 2006: 449–460). Researchers from different perspectives have been trying to address the question of how peasants and small farmers ‘hung on to their farms and their way of life’ (Holt-Giménez et al. 2021: 715–733) under the threat and pressure of industrial agriculture and the capitalist economy (Bernstein et al. 2018: 689–714). The globalized economic system is an increasing challenge for small and peasant farms (Hazell 2005: 93-101). The production model of prominent producers and retailers is forced upon them (Aubert & Perrier-Cornet 2009: 797–806), and they are vulnerable to land encroachment and loss of resources due to extractive industries (Holt-Giménez et al. 2021: 715–733).

Although small farms comprise only 12% of global farmlands, they house most of the world’s poor and food insecure, employ over 2 billion people, and produce 80% of food in Asia and Africa (Lowder et al. 2016: 16–29, FAO 2015). Therefore, smallholder agricultural growth and development are critical for poverty alleviation, food security, and improving social and economic development in underdeveloped and developing countries (Pingali et al., 2019: 368). Given the current situation of smallholder farmers in developing countries, they are generally faced with the following two options: to “move up” or “move out,” where either smallholder farmers commercialize and increase their market orientation to emerge as a profitable commercial activity or be supported to exit agriculture towards non-farm employment (Fan & Rue 2020: 13–28). Commercialization occurs when farming systems move from subsistence and semi-subsistence-oriented agriculture towards a production system based on profit maximization (Pingali et al. 2017: 77–84).

However, the peasantry remains, and small farmers still engage in alternative strategies that give them autonomy from the capitalist market (Holt-Giménez et al. 2021: 715–733, Van der Ploeg 2018). Peasant and small farms, hand in hand with agroecology, are pointed to as a pathway to more sustainable food systems (Akram-Lodhi 2021: 687–714). Peasant agriculture is defined as a distinct mode of farming carried out by small farms, based on family labour, and guided by a moral economy (Chayanov, 1966). In peasant farms, the owners manage and work the farm, which cannot be separated from the farm’s family unit (or a kin social group). Some autonomy from the market characterizes these farms and relies on internal resources, which are fundamentally self-reproduced and self-controlled (Bern-

stein et al. 2018: 689–714). The goal of their economic activity is not only the generation of profit but also the reproduction of the farm itself (Van der Ploeg, 2013) and thus, maintaining farming as their livelihood, in which the economic goal is sustaining agriculture as a means of living and a way of life.

The growth of rural textile production in Andhra (India) between the mid-sixteenth and late seventeenth century accompanied a complementary growth in certain forms of commercial agriculture. The principal food crop of the region's two river valleys and deltas was rice, which became an extensively traded crop very early in the period (Subrahmanyam 1990: 76-114). It is widely reported that while most states of India are gradually moving away from a traditional agriculture-based economy towards a more service or industry-oriented economy, North East India (Assam) is still heavily dependent on agriculture. The Upper Brahmaputra River Basin is prone to natural disasters and environmental stresses (floods, droughts, bank erosion, and delayed rainfall, among others), creating an environment of uncertainty and setting the basin back regarding socio-economic development. Nevertheless, they are the primary source of livelihood that supports a large proportion of residents of the tributaries of the Brahmaputra River Basin (Amoako & Hutton 2014: 107-121).

Agricultural transformation in developing countries may be described as the gradual and sustained transition from subsistence to diversified and specialized production (Todaro, 2001: 151-194). If development is to take place and become self-sustaining, it must include the rural areas, in general, and the agricultural sector. The core problems of widespread poverty, growing inequality, and rapid population growth all originate in the stagnation and often retrogression of economic life in rural areas (Todaro & Smith 2015: 438).

Marketing of agricultural produce is an important economic activity. Agricultural marketing has become the primary driver of the agriculture sector. The rural population of Nagaland depends on increasing agricultural productivity to raise their standard of living and income. Agricultural transformation may benefit an underdeveloped economy by strengthening the link in the development chain and lowering unemployment and rural migration. Nagaland needs an effective marketing system to support the livelihood of those employed in the economy and the general public. The state has an old and conventional agricultural marketing system. The state's agricultural produce markets and marketing systems, including those for processing and export, are established, improved, developed, and regulated under the APMC (Agriculture Produce Marketing Committee) Act, also known as the Nagaland Agricultural Produce Marketing (Development & Regulation) Act 2005.

In recent years, the transition from pure subsistence agriculture to commercialization has been initiated in some villages by changing the cropping pattern, where crops like tomatoes, potatoes, cabbages, and fruits are being increasingly cultivated for marketing purposes (Jamir, 2009: 267). The Phek district offers excellent growing potential for various horticulture crops, fruits, and vegetables. The district's native Chakhesang tribe grows a wide variety of fruits and vegetables organically, and their production of potatoes, cabbage, and fruits is crucial to the area's ability to support itself. In this context, the study explains the small-scale commercialization of agriculture in the Chakhesang tribe, its opportunities and challenges, and its socio-economic impact on the community.

Study Area:

Fig.1. Map of India showing the state of Nagaland with district Phek and the study area in yellow marking.

Nagaland state is located in the northeastern region of India, in the easternmost part of the country, bordering Arunachal state in the north, Manipur in the south, Assam in the west, and Myanmar in the east. There are sixteen districts in Nagaland. There are two tribes, Chakhesang and Pochury, in the Phek district. Chakhesang people mainly speak two dialects, *Chokri* and *Khezha*, apart from other dialects like *Sapu* and *Sumi*. Data were collected from villages of the four ranges of the Chakhesang tribe, namely the Sakraba range, Chizami range, Razebe range, and Pfutsero range.

The Chakhesang community lives in the hilly, sloppy area of the Phek District of Nagaland state, India. The area is mountainous, and its food sources are farming and forest products like fisheries, timber, and bamboo. It was formerly a biodiverse farming method comprising kitchen gardens, terrace rice culture, and shifting cropping. So, agriculture is the primary source of livelihood and economy, and bioresources are naturally available in and around the villages. Every village has its natural forest cover, and almost every clan

conserves a forest area. Every household cultivates and has a land of its own. The farmers do indigenous farming, but small commercial farming has also risen recently.

Materials and Methods

The primary data is collected from 280 households from 18 villages and four small towns, a household survey of the Chakhesang tribe to form the basis of the study. The respondents are selected through a simple random sampling technique. Each respondent was administered a semi-structured interview schedule with closed and open-ended questions. The researcher also used case studies and observation techniques to gain in-depth knowledge on changing agricultural practices in the study community. Extensive fieldwork is carried out to collect empirical data about commercial agricultural practices from different villages and government officials from the region, constituting a significant part of the methodology adopted for the study.

Results:

The inhabitants of this region have adapted their customs, traditions, lifestyles, and livelihoods to the condition of the local environment from time immemorial. Besides farming varieties of crops, farmers also rely on bioresources like wild plants and fruits for food, medicine, and household implements. With the proximity of the forest area to their villages, farmers always take advantage of nature's wealth. They forage wild herbs for food, healing wounds, and medicine. Fruits, berries, mushrooms, medicinal herbs, etc., are brought to the market. Firewood and timber from forest trees give them extra financial benefits.

The reduction in shifting cultivation and the consequent use of the fallow land for permanent cultivation for market sale has spread over the years. Farmers use wastelands for orchard farming fruits like plum, kiwi, and persimmon. Home gardens have long been a reliable source of fresh vegetables and an extension of the family garden. They now qualify as commercial assets since they produce a yearly income that is desperately needed. Farmers might experiment with domesticating wild plants in their backyard gardens or grow nurseries to maintain the diversity of their agricultural practices. Animal husbandry, particularly pig rearing and poultry raising, is another source of added income. It acts as insurance for many farmers during emergencies.

Table 1: List of Commercial Crops:

Commercial Crops	Sowing Season	Harvesting Season	Market	Type of Land	Division of Labour
Maize	March - April	August	Local market	Individual	Family labour
Yongchak	May-June	Dec-Jan. (after 6/7 years of plantation)	Kohima / Dimapur	Individual/Clan	Hired labour
Gooseberry	May-June	Jan-Feb. (after 7-8 years)	Local market	Clan	Family labour
Plum	January-March	May-June (after 2/3 years of drafting)	Dimapur	Individual/Clan	Hired labour
Kiwi	January-February	Oct-Jan. (after 2/3 years of drafting.	Kohima / Dimapur	Individual/Clan	Hired labour
Persimmon	February -March	Oct-Nov (After 2/3 years)	Kohima/ Dimapur	Individual	Family labour
Potato	January-February	May-June	Dimapur	Individual	Traditional <i>lehzekro</i> labour
Cabbage	June-Sept	July – August/ Oct-Nov (twice a year)	Local market/ Dimapur	Individual	Traditional <i>lehzekro</i> labour
Tea	May-June	March-Dec (with intervals). After 4/5 years of plantation	Local market	Individual/Clan	Family / hired labour
Cardamom	June-August	Sept-Oct (after 2/3 years)	Dimapur	Individual	Hired labour
Orange	May-June	Nov-Dec (after 5/6 years)	Local market/ Kohima	Individual	Family labour
Banana	February -March	Oct-April	Local market/ Dimapur	Individual/Clan	Traditional <i>lehzekro</i> labour
Ginger	March-April	Dec-January	Dimapur	Individual	Hired labour
Mango	May-June	August-Sept (4/5years)	Local market	Individual	Family labour

King Chilli	March-June	Aug-Sept / Oct-Nov	Local market	Individual	Family labour
Coffee	June-July	Aug-Sept (after 5/6 years)	Local market	Individual	Family labour
Apple	Jan-Feb	Oct- Nov (after 5-6 years)	Local market	Individual	Hired labour
Ground Apple	April-May	Nov-Jan	Dimapur	Individual	Family labour
Lemon	May-June	Nov-Dec (after two years)	Local market	Individual/ Clan	Family labour
Naga Dal	August	December	Local market	Individual	Family labour
Pomegrante	February-March	August-October (after 2/3 years of planting)	Local market	Individual	Family labour

Table 1. depicts the various significant crops cultivated by the farmers and their cropping seasons. The crops are mainly sold in the two leading markets of Kohima and Dimapur, apart from road-side markets, as Kohima town is the state's capital city, and Dimapur is the state's commercial hub. Truckloads of these crops are sold to the market agents at Kohima or Dimapur. Road-side markets are taken care of by the locals or the farmers themselves. Farms are owned mainly by individual landowners themselves, where few clan ownerships are also found. Cultivation is practised through various divisions of labour, where family labour, traditional *lehzekro* labour, and hired labour are utilised wherever and whenever necessary. So, from farm cultivation to land ownership and market sales, local farmers of these areas are the key players in the rise of small commercial farming.

Usage of Tools:

Among the Chakhesang, the methods and techniques of cultivation are purely based on traditional knowledge handed down from generations. Individual households generally own farmlands and are usually small landholdings of one hectare. The soil is fertile, and farms are usually in sloppy areas. Farmers use green manure from tree leaves, twigs, and grasses, and sometimes domestic animal wastes are applied into the soil. Some of the fundamental practices in commercial farming are care of seed nurseries, cutting and drafting of fruit plants, pruning, and weeding, erection of scarecrows and fences, handling and

segregation of ripe fruits, packaging into bags, and transfer of goods through mini trucks into the markets.

As farming lands are mostly sloppy, many motorable roads have recently been constructed, heavy or modern mechanical tools are not used, and chemicals and fertilizers are prohibited. Only organic farming is encouraged, and people respect the mandate for organic agriculture. The tools are primarily traditional tools like Dao, spades, and bamboo implements (modified tools). Farmers generally cannot afford modern technologies, and the terrain topography makes them use traditional farming tools. Moreover, the crops they cultivate and the size of their farms are manageable by simple tools. Traditional tools are still in use, yet some modern farming tools like power tillers, chainsaw blades, and scissors are added.

Right after harvest, they start to select and store the best seeds, and they choose healthy and wealthy seeds in terms of size, content, free from infestations, and maturity. Before storage, they dried it in the sun and kept it free from moisture for seedlings. For maize and millet, storage is generally done by hanging in the kitchen or storerooms. Paddy is stored in a big bamboo basket, and seeds of tomatoes, cucumber, and pumpkins are dried on the cloth and preserved. For food sustainability, bamboo shoots are stored and preserved in containers with filled water, chilies are dried and kept, and vegetables and other crops are usually kept in the shade and away from moist areas. Cleanliness and tidiness are maintained in storage places to avoid pest and insect visitation. Crops harvested are sorted out, arranged in sizes and shapes, and cleaned, and the unwanted parts are removed before they are sent to the market.

Division of Labour:

Due to the small amount of land ownership in the Chakhesang tribe, they mainly depend on family members for various agricultural tasks. Farms rely on family labour as the central workforce, and household members take on most of the workload related to agriculture production tasks and commercialization (Judith et al. 2023:19). Small farmers use different labour acquisition strategies when family labour is not enough. Farmers also sometimes hire seasonal workers and count on the support of relatives outside the household whenever needed. These strategies contribute to human capital and ease the workload of family members.

Lehzekro (Reciprocal group work system)

Commercial farming here is predominantly a household-based activity where family members are the primary workforce for various agricultural tasks. If required, they engage

kith and kin, wage labourers, and other farmland owners. One of the traditional workforce practices in a farming system still widely practiced is the reciprocal roster system, where labour work is mutually shared between households instead of wage payment. This system is locally known as *lehzekro*, where a group is formed by five to six individual farmers or more, irrespective of clan or khel. Once the working group is formed, work is done for every member's field one after the other, where work can be done, and only after sharing labour to all the members' fields will the work be stopped. In this way, the hiring of the labour force for farm work is reduced. As they work together, they sing songs and execute traditional farming practices where, as the song goes faster, work also goes quicker, and as the song slows down, work also slows down. During rest, they exchange traditional stories, events, and happenings of present and yesteryears. All these bring closeness to one another, solidarity, customary laws, and community support.

Role of women in farming:

Although agriculture is under the domain of men, women are the primary workforce and caretakers of crops. Despite their heavy engagement in managing household chores, women's participation in the commercial farming system indicates the successful production of the farm. As agrarian forest dwellers, the Lepcha women of Sikkim and Naga play a crucial role in agro-biodiversity management and conservation. Their authority over three levels of agriculture — the ecosystem, species, and gene — is based on their knowledge (particularly of seeds and plant breeding) and their labour (Goodrich 2012: 166–183).

Traditionally, Chakhesang women were considered subordinates to men. When it comes to commercial agriculture, it is partly reversed. Women play a big part in food safety and livelihood; They reap and lead in selling produce in the available markets. They know more about crops, wild or cultivated, their names, taste, and even their habitats. As women better understand how seed exchange networks are maintained, genetic losses are avoided through years of learning and oral tradition (Krishna, 2012). They manage the monetary transactions of their farm market and are good money-keepers. They are also the store bank of traditional knowledge from pre-harvest to post-harvest and keepers of custom and heritage. Their strength and determination in housekeeping and cultivation have become the backbone of the farming system. Women's attributes make them the harbingers for thriving commercial agriculture and better livelihood. It also increases their participation in social equality and equity, promotes leadership opportunities, and contributes toward social developments, mainly in unemployment, health, and gender equality.

Compared to men, women are more inclined to allocate their income towards their families' well-being, which includes providing healthier meals, paying for their kids' education, and providing for their health. They have a variety of functions and produce both food and cash crops. They labour on both their own and other people's plots; they work as wage labourers; they work as employers and employees; they work for pay or without pay. Although there is not much evidence about women's independent role in small-scale commercial farming, the available data shows that they make substantial contributions; for instance, in Tsupfume village in the Chakhesang area, women in commercial farms work 80 percent more than men. In other cases, women also provide more labour and management to farms than men. When we take the evidence from the Chizami village of the Chakhesang tribe, Women farmers created seed banks to conserve and circulate the indigenous varieties of seeds. They mentioned how the seed bank has given them a place to share information and close the generational gap. They prioritise establishing connections with outside markets and encouraging the sharing of seeds between farming and non-farming populations. The Chizami Women's Society connects the female farmers to the market, even empowering them politically to be a part of the village council, thus significantly allowing them to play a significant role in the decision-making process. Chizami was the first village among the Chakhesang tribe to induct women members into the village council and the Village Development Board (VDB). The capacity of women to engage in markets with knowledge and effectiveness is another factor that determines their success in commercial agriculture. Women undoubtedly have a crucial role in increasing agricultural output and rural communities' economic development.

Impact of Training:

The study found that some farmers have also gained experience through tours and workshops. Some have attended agricultural training and exposure trips. Some attended workshops on Horti-Agri farming at the district headquarters, Phek. Some went too far in states like Uttar Pradesh (UP) under the aegis of the Phek District Farmers' Union. Farmers have also attended agriculture training at the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), Dimapur. Some even went to the Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi, and Shimla for exposure and field visitation under state farmers' sponsorship.

As a result of all these efforts, several Chakhesang villages turned into hotspots for the cultivation of commercial crops. Consequently, the Horticulture Department of Nagaland recognised some of the Chakhesang villages in the study area; namely, Tsupfume Village was named the 'First Vegetable Village' in Nagaland in 2005. Zhavame Village was

called ‘Vegetable Village’ in 2010, and Sakraba Village as ‘Cardamom Village’ in 2015. Major crops, fruits, and plantations commercially cultivated are Cabbages, Potatoes, Gingers, Maize, Naga Dal, King Chilli, Plum, Kiwi, Ground Apple, Banana, Gooseberry, Cardamom, and *Yongchak*.

Fig. 2. Photos of commercial farms:

Market:

One of the main criteria for improving livelihood and food security in rural farming is access to markets for selling and buying goods. It also increases the hope for cash income and bridges the marketing gap, thus improving their overall living standard. Commercial agriculture is one answer for indigenous farmers where this goal can be achieved. Every farmer participates in small commercial agriculture either as an owner or labourer.

The Chakhesang farmers primarily sell their crops at the local market and Kohima, the state’s capital, or transport to the Dimapur market, the state’s commercial hub. Dimapur is around 220 km from Phek headquarters by road, and NH 29 passes through this route. Farmers do not have permanent market links, dealers, or contracts like other commercial farming states. At times, farmers feel the pressure of demand for their products. However, they fall short of supply as it is a small family farm, and people do not do large-scale farming because of ignorance, inexperience, unawareness, financial problems, the time factor, complacency, subsistent attitude, and many other factors. Too many check gates and tax collections from various organisations also hamper their activities. Farmers fall under the

hands of wholesale dealers in terms of price negotiation. All these unorganised and unsystematic markets make the farmers unsatisfied regarding their sales.

Fig.3: Road-side Market

Fig.4: Chakhesang Organic Market

Socio-economic impact:

The Chakhesang community, like any other hill tribe of northeast India, is historically known for subsistence-based agricultural practices. However, with the advent of the market economy, many farmers are venturing into commercial farming. As stated by one respondent, *‘Yes, people are moving more towards commercial farming, not forsaking traditional land usage systems but more improvised; wastelands are converted into orchards and homestead gardens for commercial purposes. Every household is doing small commercial farms for extra earnings, construction and maintenance of roads.’*¹ In the contemporary era of the market economy, the decision of which crops to grow and how to cultivate the land has been heavily impacted by the necessity to make money from agriculture. One of the respondents says, *‘Even though it is a small commercial farm, it takes care of family financial expenditures in one way. Working also gives us a healthy mind and body.’*² The Chakhesang farmers are investing in permanent vegetable farms in backyard gardens and orchards in addition to mixed-crop rice farming. This gives farmers the much-needed cash flow and creates opportunities for smaller farmers to make money by working every day in such farms, plantations, and orchards on a part-time basis.

It is found that commercial agriculture brings unity to the family; as farmers learn to work together, they become closer, and family ties are expanded. They respect and serve each other as they unitedly work for the common good. The relationship between Kith and Kins becomes more robust and better. As described by one of the respondents, *‘I got lots of experiences through farming, more contacts were created, and relationships increased, which built up my confidence level too, inside and outside the village, bringing the world closer to me. Environmental awareness was instilled; nature is a gift, and we must respect nature.’*³ Hard work and dedication in farming give rich dividends and confidence, which builds and boosts one’s stature. It pushes them to get involved in social events and creates an environment where farmers can lead. The community recognises and regards them as

successful farmers and looks up to them for farming skills. It gives the farmers' families financial relief regarding their children's education and household expenditures. In the words of one of the respondents, *'Commercial farming helps in our daily life and gives financial relief, but it is a small farm. The expenses, time, effort, etc, should also be considered. We feel satisfied and at peace with ourselves when we look at our farm blooming and our honest, hard labour. Sometimes, I imagine, big commercial farms.'*⁴ It shows the farmers' optimism and plans for financial security in the region. It also brings employment and encourages entrepreneurship and agri-business opportunities in the community.

The Chakhesang tribe has specific customary laws about exploiting natural resources, including land management. Nevertheless, as shared by one respondent, *'Customary law applies for commercial farming also; we should not take it out of our tradition, but there are no restrictions in legal farming. He said, no one can stop you from farming (chuckles); instead, everyone should do farming.'*⁵ One incredibly inspiring and desirable aspect felt by commercial farmers is the acceptance and support of the community for their commercial organic cultivation. As it is a small-scale commercial farm, not much of the land area and forest cover are used, and still, the profits gained could release the farmers from their financial constraints. The community also invites them to seminars and workshops, sales days, and exhibitions supporting the cultivation. Commercial farming has impacted a lot of individual approaches, too. It has raised the value of appreciation for nature and food. One respondent said, *'Farming brings society and environment closer to you. It develops your farming skills, improves your health, and supports family income. Moreover, organic farming is the best.'*⁶ The concern for the growth of one's health, environment, personal hygiene, and work culture can be felt as one experiences commercial agricultural practices.

For the Chakhesang' it is customarily said that it is a shame to beg for food, which means we should not be lazy. In one way, agriculture is not an option but a livelihood. Commercial agriculture has redefined the work culture in the lives of the community. Most households in a village have a farm and a field to cultivate. Even the slogan "Work and Eat" has been promoted. As the population lives in a world of demand for food, commercial agriculture has motivated and moved the community into a work culture for food security. As it mobilized the whole village and the entire village participated in farming activities, the agricultural department and Nagaland's government granted recognition to the villages accordingly.

Education is essential for agriculture farmers; teaching them how commercial agriculture may lead to a better understanding of resource management in this region. Most farmers in this region are literate and have at least a minimum educational background. Every farmer stresses the implications of education and that modern farming and marketing are becoming more problematic without education. Farmers need to know how to communicate and maintain a relationship with the outside world, get information and use modern technologies, handle market links, and stay competitive for the development and betterment of livelihood. At the same time, we must preserve and conserve the bioresources, which are the lifeline of food security.

As farmers experience goods transactions in the market, they learn about the market system and build and maintain trustworthy relationships with the customers and the outside world, like the market agents and stakeholders. One of the farmers proudly stated about the outcome of commercial agriculture, *'Only because of this cultivation, we are surviving now. Traditional agriculture can no longer sustain us. As we are unemployed and no other befitting jobs available, the small-scale commercial farm has become our sole bread earner, where we can only rely upon.'*⁷ This indicates the best available livelihood opportunities for the people in the region.

Opportunities:

Small-scale commercial farming encourages the growth of agriculture, food security, and livelihood opportunities for the farmers. The future of sustainable agriculture depends on the performance of small and marginal farmers, as they play a crucial pillar in modern agriculture. Commercial agriculture enables the cultivation of high-demand commercial crops like cabbages, potatoes, maize, bananas, plums, and kiwi. This has also helped solidify the Chakhesang farmers' presence in the market system. One of the respondents stated, *'Our village, our area, can also become the food bowl of Nagaland. We are small farmers but have good land, a favourable climate, lots of nature's gifts, hardworking people, dedication, and honesty. We cannot always look for government jobs. If we want to be rich and developed, farming is one area where we can create it, so we need to cultivate, teach, and spread the power of commercial farming.'*⁸

Farming not only sustains them in their diet and nourishment but also the income or profit from the sale of crops, which helps them with children's education fees and household maintenance. They also become economically more robust. As they get exposure to outside

village life and build relationships, it assists them in improving farming practices, e.g., using modern farming tools (grass-cutter, power tiller) and cultivating exotic crops (kiwi, persimmon). This also helps in expanding their market system. They no longer constrain themselves in their villages, but through marketing channels and contacts, they learn and get inspired. As the use of any chemicals is restricted, organic crops bring more dividends and are more customer-friendly. With many health issues, customers are more into organic goods, which helps promote organic crops and market exchange. Knowledge expansion has also taught them the importance of ecological conservation and the need to protect nature.

Farmers are also invited and encouraged to participate in local sales day and environment awareness programs, where they showcase their crop harvest. This helps propagate traditional farming methods and conserve diminishing local species. It also creates and stimulates entrepreneurship and employment. One of the respondents commented that *'for commercial agriculture, the scope is huge, developed nations started with agriculture, whether we are late or not, regarding agriculture there is nothing to do with backward or not. To move forward, we need the government to coordinate with all the stakeholders and work together for development. Our state is so blessed with land, water, and nature that no family ever experiences dire poverty, which may be the problem of not becoming a tycoon agriculturist, especially in our area. If not, we have everything from the farmer's side to farm.'*⁹

The entire Himalayan range is favourable for growing various fruits, vegetables, and cash crops. Small areas with their micro-climatic conditions provide suitable sites for growing particular crops, such as citrus fruits, plums, bananas, and pineapples; vegetables such as tomatoes, potatoes, and cabbage; other cash crops like ginger, chilies, and cardamom; and flowers such as orchids, marigolds, and chrysanthemums. The present trends toward rapid expansion of horticultural crops will have positive implications for improving the food and economic security of the hill farmers (Partap 2011: 33 – 52).

Most marginal farmers in developing countries practice traditional agriculture using very little or no agrochemicals. By adopting organic agriculture, which requires less financial input while placing more reliance on natural and human resources, farmers could move towards more sustainable agricultural practices (Scialabba 2000: 28-31). Improving the sustainability of the farming production system in marginal areas and providing market access for the deprived hold the key to the mass reduction of poverty (Jimenez, 2006).

Challenges:

Farmers do face problems in their farming system. When asked, one of the farmers, who was the Former President of the Phek District Farmers' Union, said, *'We get contracts, offers, deals with the bigger dealers/traders, etc., but we do not have that cultivation capacity to capture the market; backwardness is the problem, we do not get government assistance in time, no facilities and infrastructures available (cold storage/ electricity/ roads). Technological development is a far cry. We must also educate the farmers on persistence, hard work, dedication, care for nature, etc. Proper deliberate planning from regional to state through government agencies must be executed.'*¹⁰

Low productivity and a risky agricultural production environment in the northeast region are the primary causes of deteriorated rural livelihood. Ironically, this has happened despite the existence of a large number of production possibilities for a wide range of fruit and vegetables, flowers and herbs, spices, and plantation crops in the region; much of these could be processed and gainfully traded in the rest of the country and worldwide (Barah 2007: 13). Failure of the market is one of the worst enemies of the farmers; though crops are harvested, there is no market for the crops. One such instance is the cultivation of ground apples by the farmers, especially Zelome farmers of the Chakhesang tribe. In the initial stage of farm production of this ground apple, the market was very successful, but the year next, the market completely dropped, and all the farmers' harvests were lost and rotten, which devastated the cultivation of ground apple.

Thus, farmers face a huge problem due to price fluctuation and unawareness of the market system, where they are at the mercy of the big dealers in the towns. Hill agriculture has limitations due to remoteness and inaccessibility. Smallholdings, low productivity, poor post-production management, inadequate marketing and networks, poor infrastructure, and a lack of entrepreneurship are some of the restrictions that hill agriculture faces. Farmers also face obstacles in their farming transactions, as they pay money to too many check gates to reach Dimapur town to sell their goods. They also face problems with tax payments to various organisations.

Conclusion:

The importance of biodiversity and plant genetic resources in human survival and food security makes it vital to maintain crop diversity in farmers' fields, especially in 'hot spots' of plant genetic diversity. Indeed, this is considered a 'global life insurance policy' by the Convention on Biological Diversity (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity 2001). As rightly said, if educated youth choose to live in villages and launch the new agriculture movement based on the integrated application of science and social wisdom,

our untapped demographic dividend will become our greatest strength (Swaminathan 2013: 13). Subsistence farmers worldwide play a significant role in preserving agro-biodiversity by cultivating many crop species, especially in environments where high-yielding crops and livestock do not prosper (Goodrich 2012: 166-183). However, globalization, in one way, brings instability to farmers of this region as enormous food commodities enter the common market at a cheaper rate and in more abundance; farmers stand at the mercy of the market agents.

The most important 'sustainable' agriculture systems introduced recently are integrated agroecological, pest management, and mainly organic farming. However, organic farming might be practiced differently in different regions (Genghini et al. 2006: 3077–3094). Considering the unique and special agroecological and socio-economic setting, the Green Revolution failed to climb the Himalayan heights. The National Policy on Farmers outlined by the National Commission on Farmers (NCOF, 2006) has strongly recommended that the National Policy on Agriculture should have a unique parallel window on hill agriculture so that it can commensurate strategies for hill agriculture research, technology, and marketing could be established. It recommended strengthening the interdependency and partnership between all the sectors of agriculture, viz., crops, horticulture, livestock, fisheries, forestry, and the associated natural resources (Partap 2011: 33–52).

The financial gains from selling off their produce, the surplus, easy and affordable cultivation make the farmers shift to commercial farming. Unlike traditional farming, in the presence of rich nutrient soil, commercial farming among the Chakhesang community brings more dividends into the life of these farmers in terms of monetary profits where it helps in covering up lots of family financial expenditures. The effort is not merely selling the product of agriculture but ensuring that the community grows together with the traditional cultivation method in this modernized world and maintains its livelihood. The support from the community in their selling transaction of organic crops, acknowledgments and participation in local awareness programs and workshops, the training, schemes, visitation, and encouragement from the horticulture department have given them the sustenance to the fullest.

As they gain experience in loss and profit in their farming practices, communications and relationships with the outside world have become stronger, more confident, and noticeable. They have more contacts and more access to markets and dealers now. They even find ways to face repercussions by building trust and learning business ethics. With

the experience of the income from commercial farming, almost all the farmers are shifting towards it, not abandoning their traditional farms. Though the farmers have supported commercial agriculture, most were found to have a moderate motivation level due to their lack of efficiency and financial burdens. Nevertheless, the agriculture trend is shifting towards small commercial farming.

Farmers, the guardians of agriculture, must be protected with sustainable and secure livelihoods. From the above study, we can conclude that even though it is a small family commercial farming system, farmers benefit from their farming, which is reflected in their livelihoods. It has significantly contributed to food safety and checks unemployment issues. Not only that, it has also broadened the farmers' scope of economic and social development. However, when we envisage the system, the need for commercial farming should be maintained to conserve the now abundant bioresources lest the bio-economy resources get exhausted.

End Note

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- ¹ Sanyi Rume, Male, 57 years old, Zelome Village
 - ² Vezokho Vesu, Male, 55 years old. Pholami Village
 - ³ Vesato Lohe, Male, 44 years old, Sakraba Village
 - ⁴ Khrotelo Elah, Male, 52 years old. Enhulumi Village
 - ⁵ Mikha Kenye, Male, 64 years old, Zapami Village
 - ⁶ Vivotso Domeh, Male, 53 years old, Zhavame Village
 - ⁷ Khrotezo Wezah, Male, 43 years old, Chizami Town
 - ⁸ Khazi Lea, Male, 68 years old, Tsupfume Village
 - ⁹ Neisa puro, Male, 49 years old, Enhulumi Village
 - ¹⁰ Khazi Lea, Male, 68 years old, Tsupfume Village

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